

Chromic Acid Oxidation of Some Tertiary Indan-1-ols

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2-Benzylphenylacetic acid, the key intermediate for the synthesis of dibenzo [a, d]-cyclohepta-1,4-dien-10-one¹, has been prepared earlier by the chain extension of 2-benzylbenzoic acid, following two different routes¹⁻². The interest for an alternative convenient synthesis of 2-benzylphenylacetic acid directed our attention to the work of Feiser and Szmuszkowicz³ who had reported that oxidation of cyclic tertiary alcohols with a suspension of CrO₃ in glacial acetic acid provided good yields of keto-acids. Using this method, we oxidised 1-phenylindan-1-ol (I), prepared by the interaction of indan-1-one and phenylmagnesium bromide, and obtained 89% yield of 2-benzoylphenylacetic acid which was reduced by Huang-Minlon procedure to 2-benzylphenylacetic acid in 76% yield.

The initial success obtained prompted us to study similar oxidation of other tertiary indan-1-ols. For this purpose, 1-benzylindan-1-ol (II), 1- α -naphthylindan-1-ol (III), and 1-phenyl-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-ol (IV) were prepared by the Grignard reaction. Oxidation of the carbinols (II) and (IV) afforded poor yields of 2-(phenylacetyl)phenylacetic acid and 2-benzoyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid, respectively; carbinol (III) yielded only intractable products.

1-Phenylindan-1-ol (I).—A solution of indan-1-one (25.1 g.) in dry ether (75 ml) was gradually added with stirring during $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. to a well-cooled ethereal solution of phenylmagnesium bromide⁴, prepared from Mg (6.0 g.) and bromobenzene (39.6 g.). After addition, the reaction mixture was stirred for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. at the room temperature and then refluxed with stirring for 2 hr. Next day the complex was decomposed with a cold saturated solution of NH₄Cl, the ether layer separated, and the aqueous layer thoroughly extracted with ether. The combined extracts were dried (Na₂SO₄) and the ether evaporated. The oily residue was distilled under reduced pressure to afford (I) (25.5 g.), b.p. 134-35°/1mm. (Found: C, 85.3; H, 6.4. C₁₅H₁₄O requires C, 85.7; H, 6.6%).

1-Benzylindan-1-ol (II).—To an ice-cooled ethereal solution of benzylmagnesium chloride⁵, prepared from Mg (4.86 g.) and benzyl chloride (25.3 g.), was added dropwise with stirring a solution of indan-1-one (26.4 g.) in dry ether (100 ml). The vigorous reaction during the course of addition was moderated by efficient cooling and controlling the rate of addition. After completion of the addition, the reaction mixture was worked up as above and the product was purified by distillation under reduced pressure to yield (II) (22.4 g.), b.p. 155-56°/2mm. (Found: C, 86.1; H, 6.8. C₁₆H₁₆O requires C, 85.7; H, 7.1%).

1- α -Naphthylindan-1-ol (III).—A solution of indan-1-one (31.0 g.) in dry ether (75 ml) was allowed to react in a manner similar to the procedure, detailed above, with an ethereal solution of α -naphthylmagnesium bromide, prepared from Mg (6.0 g.) and α -bromonaphthalene (52.2 g.). The product, on crystallisation from benzene-petroleum (b.p. 60-80°),

1. Leonard *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 5078.

2. Rigaddy and Nedelec, *Compt. rend.*, 1953, **236**, 1287.

3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3352.

4. "Organic Syntheses", J. Wiley & Sons, 1946, Vol. I, p. 550.

5. *Ibid.*, p. 471.

furnished (III) as tiny prisms (21.0 g.), m.p. 134-35°. (Found: C, 88.0; H, 5.8. $C_{19}H_{16}O$ requires C, 87.7; H, 6.1%).

1-*Phenyl-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-ol* (IV).—The poor solubility of 5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one in ether necessitated the use of THF for the Grignard reaction. A solution of 5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one⁶ (10.0 g.) in dry THF (60 ml) was allowed to react similarly as above with a solution of phenylmagnesium bromide in THF, prepared from Mg (1.3 g.) and bromobenzene (7.8 g.) in dry THF (20 ml). It was worked up as above except that ethyl acetate was used as the extracting solvent. Evaporation of the solvent left a brown sticky solid, the benzene solution of which was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina. The solid, isolated after evaporation of benzene, was recrystallised from benzene to furnish (IV) as colorless rectangular prisms (4.5 g.), m.p. 122-23°. (Found: C, 75.80; H, 6.30. $C_{17}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 75.55; H, 6.66%).

2-*Benzoylphenylacetic Acid*.—To a stirred solution of the carbinol (I, 5.6 g.) in glacial acetic acid (180 ml) at 25° was added CrO_3 (1.0 g.). Within a few seconds the solution darkened with dissolution of CrO_3 and the temperature rose to 30° at which it was maintained while more CrO_3 (11.0 g.) was added in portions. After stirring for an hour, the brown mixture was treated with an equal volume of water and extracted thoroughly with ether (50 ml $\times$ 4). The ether layer was washed well with water, extracted with 5% aqueous NaOH (20 ml $\times$ 3), and the cooled alkaline extract acidified with HCl (conc.) when a yellowish solid separated. Recrystallisations from ethyl acetate-light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) furnished the pure *keto-acid* as colorless rectangular plates (5.0 g.), m.p. 130-31°. (Found: C, 74.8; H, 5.1. $C_{15}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 75.0; H, 5.0%).

2-(*Phenylacetyl*)*phenylacetic Acid*.—A solution of the carbinol (II, 2.0 g.) in glacial acetic acid (75 ml) was oxidised with CrO_3 (6.0 g.) at 50° as above. The product on several crystallisations from light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) furnished the *keto-acid* as colorless rectangular prisms (0.5 g.), m.p. 118-19°. (Found: C, 75.2; H, 5.9. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 75.6; H, 5.5%).

2-*Benzoyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenylacetic Acid*.—A solution of the carbinol (IV, 2.4 g.) in glacial acetic acid (90 ml) was oxidised with CrO_3 (6.0 g.) at 30° as above. The reaction mixture was worked up as above except that ethyl acetate was used as the extracting solvent. Evaporation of the solvent, followed by crystallisations from ethyl acetate, afforded the *keto-acid* as colorless, elongated needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 168-70°. (Found: C, 67.6; H, 5.6. $C_{17}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 68.0; H, 5.3%).

2-*Benzylphenylacetic Acid*.—A mixture of 2-benzoylphenylacetic acid (5.0 g.), 80% hydrazine hydrate (6.0 ml), and NaOH (4.0 g.) in diethylene glycol (10 ml) was refluxed at 150-60° for 1 hr. and then distilled slowly, raising the temperature to 205-15° at which it was maintained for 3 hr. The residue was treated with ice, acidified, and the precipitate collected and dried. Crystallisations from light petroleum (b. p. 60-80°) furnished the pure *acid* as colorless needles (3.8 g.), m.p. 89-90° (lit.¹⁻² m.p. 88°; 93-94°; 95.5°).